

Workflow #1: Agricultural droughts

Climate Risk and Vulnerability Assessment of the Region of Murcia (REGMURCIA CLIMAAX)

Table 1 Data overview workflow for Relative droughts

Component	Data Used & Source	Purpose / Role in Workflow
Hazard data	Monthly total precipitation for NUTS3 regions, from the ensemble average of five CMIP6 GCMs (GFDL-ESM4, IPSL-CM6A-LR, MPI-ESM1-2-HR, MRI-ESM2-0, UKESM1-0-LL), bias-adjusted for historical (1981–2015) and future periods (2031–2060, 2071–2100) under SSP126, SSP370, and SSP585 scenarios. Hazard is calculated as the probability of exceeding the median of severe regional precipitation deficits.	Quantifies drought hazard by measuring the frequency and severity of precipitation deficits, enabling comparison between regions and periods.
Exposure data	Multi-dimensional exposure dataset covering agricultural land, livestock, water competition, population (for drinking water demand), etc. Quantified using a non-compensatory model and Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA) across NUTS-level spatial units	Estimates the relative exposure of each region to drought impacts across different sectors and use categories.
Vulnerability data	Proxy indicators for economic, social, and infrastructural aspects of vulnerability to drought	Captures region-specific susceptibility to drought based on socioeconomic and infrastructural factors.
Risk output	Normalized hazard, exposure, and vulnerability indices aggregated into a relative drought risk score per NUTS3 region. Added neighborhood regions	Provides a comparative ranking of drought risk among sub-national regions, useful for prioritizing resource allocation and adaptation efforts.

We analyzed, for all possible cases, the three scenarios and the near- and far-future periods, as well as the historical one, considering both hazard and risk for Murcia Province and Region (E620). Values are extracted for the tables given by the application. The results are shown in [Table 2](#).

Table 2 Summary results for relative drought.

Scenario	Hazard	Exposure	Vulnerability	Risk	Risk Cat.
historic	0.822	1.000	0.413	0.339	2
ssp126_ff	0.860	1.000	0.907	0.777	4
ssp126_nf	0.810	0.952	0.885	0.682	4
ssp370_ff	0.819	0.999	0.697	0.570	3
ssp370_nf	0.815	1.000	0.683	0.557	3
ssp585_ff	0.756	0.997	0.918	0.692	4

Note: FF: Far Future; NF: Near Future

In the historical period, risk is low–moderate (0.339, Cat. 2) because vulnerability remains relatively low, even though hazard and exposure are high. Across all future scenarios, exposure stays nearly constant at about 1.0, so the main driver of differences is vulnerability. In SSP126 (both far and near future), vulnerability becomes very high (>0.88), resulting in high risk (Cat. 4). In SSP370, vulnerability is more moderate (~0.68–0.70), which keeps the risk at a medium–high level (Cat. 3). In SSP585, although hazard slightly decreases, vulnerability increases strongly (>0.88), leading again to high risk (Cat. 4). Overall, future scenarios consistently show higher risk than the historical period, driven mainly by increasing vulnerability rather than by changes in hazard or exposure.

Regarding the relative Droughts, in general, CARM is almost always worse off than its surrounding areas, or at least in the most severe situations. [Figure 1](#) shows that the risk for CARM increases under climate change scenarios compared to the rest of the Spanish provinces. The graph shows that CARM is the province most affected even under lower hazard conditions. It is consistently more exposed than the others (most, if not all), and this difference is particularly pronounced in SSP126, which indicates that CARM is the first and most severely affected.

Figure 1 Line chart for historic and future relative drought risk in the CARM (NUTS2).

The CLIMAAX Toolbox displays the values for each province within a given region. However, since CARM is a single-province region, this poses a limitation. To address this, we modified the code in order to enable comparisons with the nearest provinces. In this regard, [Figure 2](#) indicate that CARM consistently emerges as one of the most affected provinces, with risk levels exceeding those of neighbouring Alicante and Albacete in nearly all future scenarios. By mid-century, under both ssp126 and ssp585, CARM already shows markedly higher values, approaching those of Almería, the province with the overall maximum. Towards 2080, the persistence of these elevated risks across all scenarios confirms CARM’s structural vulnerability, as it remains systematically above its inland and northern neighbours.

Figure 2: Risk in focal areas. The focal area is selected as the surrounding provinces to CARM

Figure 3 illustrates the distribution of risk categories across the selected focal area. The spatial pattern clearly identifies the CARM as one of the provinces facing the highest risk levels by the end of the century, exceeded only by a few neighbouring territories in Andalusia. This outcome reinforces the earlier finding that the CARM consistently ranks above Alicante and Albacete, while remaining close to Almería in overall drought risk category. The persistence of this signal across different models and scenarios points to a structural concentration of drought risk in the CARM, underscoring the need to prioritize drought adaptation.

Figure 3: Projected risk categories across southern Spain under scenario ssp585 by 2080.